

**GRADUATE TRACER STUDY: ASSESSING ALIGNMENT OF DR. CARLOS S.
LANTING COLLEGE'S MARITIME EDUCATION WITH INDUSTRY
DEMANDS AND GRADUATE CAREER OUTCOMES**

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Graduate Tracer Study: Assessing Alignment of Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College's Maritime Education with Industry Demands and Graduate Career Outcomes

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Abstract

The Graduate Tracer Study examines Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College's maritime education programs and their impact on graduates' professional development. The study uses a graduate tracer approach to gather data from alumni, focusing on employment rates, practicality, job satisfaction, and professional development opportunities. Results show a significant proportion of recent graduates are employed in critical maritime industries. However, discrepancies exist between the academic curriculum and industry demands, suggesting potential for improvement. The study recommends increased diversity, improved practical training, strengthened industry-university partnerships, career assistance, and continuous professional growth. It also emphasizes research and innovation expansion and student participation in curriculum creation.

Keywords: *graduate tracer, maritime education, graduate employment, curriculum alignment, professional development*

Introduction

The worldwide maritime business is undergoing a period of rapid evolution and expansion, which has resulted in an unprecedented demand for maritime professionals that possess adequate preparation (Alop, 2019; Boonadir et al., 2020; Johnson, 2020; Lau et al., 2021, 2021; Simmons & McLean, 2020). Respected in the maritime education industry, Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College has been aggressive in developing competent personnel capable of achieving success in this ever-changing business. The objective of this research is to assess the extent to which the educational programs offered by the college correspond to the current demands of the marine sector and to determine how this corresponds with the professional achievements of the college's alumni. Through the examination of many determinants, including employment rates and the applicability of the curriculum, this study provides an all-encompassing synopsis of the vocational trajectories followed by the institution's former students.

The significance of this study is evident not only in its reflection of past and current achievements but also in its potential to guide future enhancements. Through an in-depth examination of employment trends, job satisfaction, opportunities for professional growth, and feedback on educational offerings, valuable insights into the strengths and areas for improvement within the college's policies and practices are gained. These insights are crucial for policymakers and educational administrators as they adjust the academic direction to ensure that graduates are not only prepared for today's maritime challenges but also equipped to lead tomorrow's innovations in the industry.

With a strong commitment to academic excellence and a focus on staying abreast of industry trends, Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College is prepared to navigate the changing landscape, reaffirming its role as a key contributor to the global maritime community. This study serves as a testament to the college's accomplishments and a guide for continuous improvement, ensuring that the institution remains a beacon of excellence in maritime education for future generations.

Objective

The study aims to evaluate the career trajectories, employment status, job satisfaction, and professional development of maritime graduates to identify trends, challenges, and opportunities in the maritime industry. It will determine the employment rate, assess the relevance of maritime education curriculum, identify employment sectors, evaluate job satisfaction, explore professional development opportunities, and gather feedback for improvement.

Literature Review

The maritime industry plays a crucial role in global trade, transportation, and economic development (Jacks & Pendakur, 2010; Lane & Pretes, 2020), and the success of this industry largely depends on the quality and skills of its workforce (Maria Chala & Bouranta, 2021; Wahl & Kongsvik, 2017; Yan & Wang, 2022). Maritime graduates, who undergo specialized education and training, are essential to the industry's continued growth and competitiveness (Bila, 2022; E. Mohamed & Elnoury, 2023; Ng et al., 2011).

Existing literature suggests that the career trajectories (Chiong, 2023), employment status (Muslu, 2020), job satisfaction (Muktar Sitompul et al., 2020), and professional development of maritime graduates (Jiang, 2021) are crucial factors in understanding the industry's health and future prospects.

Recent studies have highlighted the evolving nature of maritime education, which now encompasses a broader range of subjects beyond traditional shipping-focused topics (Lau & Ng, 2015). Interdisciplinary training platforms that incorporate business knowledge, management skills, and technological advancements are becoming increasingly important to equip graduates with the diverse

competencies required in the modern maritime industry (Ying et al., 2021). This shift in maritime education aims to produce well-rounded professionals who can navigate the complex and dynamic landscape of the industry.

One study found that strengthening vocational awareness among students can reinforce their aspiration to pursue seafaring careers, which is crucial in addressing the persistent challenge of attracting talent to the maritime industry (Wong, 2021). Another study emphasized the need to align students' expectations with the program delivery to ensure a better fit between their aspirations and the industry's needs (Lau et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the growing demand for specialized knowledge and skills in areas such as risk management, maritime law, and cyber-risk management highlights the importance of continually updating maritime curricula to keep pace with the industry's evolving requirements (Alop, 2019; Boonadir et al., 2020; Lau et al., 2021; Ying et al., 2021; Yuen et al., 2022).

Methodology

The present study employed the descriptive approach to ascertain the employment status of graduates with a BS in Marine Transportation and BS in Marine Engineering. Additionally, quantitative analysis was employed by the researchers to gather data and evaluate the responses of the participants. The present survey used a purposive selection technique to select a cohort of graduates that is typical of the institution. This ensures that the insights obtained are both pertinent and particular to the marine programs offered by the college. As a consequence of the participants' occupations and the restricted availability of contact details among the respondents, the study received responses from a mere 98 maritime graduates. Among these, 57.1 percent ($n=56$) held a BS in Marine Transportation, while 42.9 percent (42 out of 98) graduated with a BS in Marine Engineering. The sample for this study is restricted to graduates who completed the survey questionnaire that was distributed to them via email and Google Forms; no further responses were received via social networking sites or messaging applications. The primary instrument utilized in this research was the graduate tracer questionnaire obtained from the institution's job placement office. The survey comprises five sections: initially, respondent demographics; second, educational background; third, information on employability; fourth, skills and knowledge; and finally, professional accomplishments. Consistent with ethical principles, the study ensures the utmost protection of participant privacy and data confidentiality. Consent is sought from all participants, and the research's objectives are explained in an open manner. Although the research is comprehensive in its reach, it approaches its limits with a discerning eye, acknowledging the possibility of non-response bias and the difficulties associated with obtaining an alumni sample that is entirely representative. Following the collection of the data, descriptive statistics were applied to compute and analyze the questionnaire responses, including frequency count, percentage, weighted mean, and standard deviation.

Results and Discussion

The study analyzes the professional trajectories and educational experiences of maritime graduates from Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College, revealing key trends and patterns in their transition into the workforce. It examines job satisfaction, curriculum relevance, and professional advancement opportunities, offering both praise and critique for strengths and areas needing enhancement. The findings can inform policy improvements and promote maritime education programs.

General Information

Table 1. Respondents General Information

<i>Indicators</i>		<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Civil Status	Single	76	77.6%
	Married	22	22.4%
	Separated/Divorced/Married but not living with spouse	0	0.0%
	Single Parent	0	0.0%
	Widow or Widower	0	0.0%
Sex	Male	92	93.9%
	Female	6	6.1%
Age	23 y.o.	2	2.0%
	24 y.o.	5	5.1%
	25 y.o.	13	13.3%
	26 y.o.	22	22.4%
	27 y.o.	10	10.2%
	28 y.o.	17	17.3%
	29 y.o.	13	13.3%
	30 y.o.	8	8.2%
	above 30 y.o.	8	8.2%

N=98. Mean (SD); Age=27.6 (2.7) Min=23, Max=37

The Respondents General Information in Table 1 sheds light on the profiles of 98 respondents who are graduates of BS Maritime Transportation and BS Marine Engineering. This data reveals key insights into the personal characteristics of individuals in this professional field.

As presented in Table 1, the majority of respondents are single (77.6%), with married individuals constituting 22.4% of the sample. Notably, there are no respondents who are separated, divorced, married but not living with their spouse, single parents, or widows/widowers. This demographic distribution may reflect the age range of the respondents, which predominantly falls between 23 and 30 years old, with an average age of 27.6 years ($SD = 2.7$). The age data indicates a young workforce, with the youngest at 23 and the eldest at 37 years old.

In terms of gender, the field shows a significant male dominance, with 93.9% male respondents compared to 6.1% female. This skew towards male respondents could be indicative of existing gender trends within the maritime sector, which has traditionally been male-dominated.

The age distribution is relatively spread out, with the largest age groups being 26 years old (22.4%) and 28 years old (17.3%). The data indicate a trend of individuals completing their education in their mid to late 20s.

Educational Background

This section of the study analyzes educational background, examining factors influencing academic choices and challenges. Essential tables provide insights into respondents' experiences, highlighting the importance of data analysis in education.

Table 2. Respondents Graduation Statistics by Degree and Year

Indicators		Frequency	Percentage
Degree	BS Marine Transportation	56	57.1%
	BS Marine Engineering	42	42.9%
Year Graduated	2017	2	2.0%
	2018	25	25.5%
	2019	23	23.5%
	2020	17	17.3%
	2021	13	13.3%
	2022	18	18.4%

Regarding the degree, the graduates are almost evenly split between BS Marine Transportation (57.1%) and BS Marine Engineering (42.9%), suggesting a balanced interest and possibly job opportunities in both areas of the maritime field.

The graduation year data reflects a steady stream of graduates with a slight increase in recent years, particularly in 2018 (25.5%) and 2022 (18.4%), which may correspond to a growth in the maritime industry or in educational opportunities.

The cross-tabulation of professional examinations passed by graduates of BS Marine Transportation and BS Marine Engineering degrees (Table 3) illustrates distinct paths in professional certification aligned with their specialized training. The data exhibit a clear division of professional qualifications between the two degrees.

Table 3. Cross-Tabulation of Professional Examinations Passed by Degree

	Degree		Total
	BS Marine Transportation	BS Marine Engineering	
OIC Engineering watch	0	25	25
OIC Navigation Watch	37	0	37
Civil Service Examination Professional	1	0	1
PCG Aptitude Battery Test (PCGABT) not yet taken	0	1	1
	18	16	34
Total	56	42	98

All 25 graduates who passed the Officer in Charge (OIC) Engineering Watch exam were from the BS Marine Engineering program, which aligns with the technical and engineering focus of their studies. Conversely, the OIC Navigation Watch exam was exclusively passed by 37 graduates from the BS Marine Transportation program, reflecting their navigational and operational training.

Interestingly, there was only one instance each of a graduate from the BS Marine Transportation program passing the Civil Service Examination Professional and a graduate from the BS Marine Engineering program passing the Philippine Coast Guard Aptitude Battery Test (PCGABT). These instances may indicate individual pursuits of broader career opportunities beyond their specialized fields.

A notable portion of graduates has not yet taken any professional examinations, accounting for 18 from the BS Marine Transportation and 16 from the BS Marine Engineering programs, summing up to 34 out of 98 graduates. This suggests that a significant number of graduates may be in the early stages of their career development or may be pursuing employment opportunities that do not require these certifications.

The motivations for students pursuing degrees in maritime studies are multifaceted, with the data indicating a variety of influences and aspirations (Table 4). A significant proportion of students (41%) reported being influenced by parents or relatives in their decision to pursue their maritime course, which suggests that familial expectations and guidance play a critical role in their educational choices. This factor is closely followed by the opportunity for employment abroad, cited by 38% of respondents, indicating the global nature of the maritime industry and the allure of international career opportunities as a decisive factor for many students.

Table 4. *Reasons for taking the course/pursuing the degree*

	<i>n</i>	<i>% (n/N)</i>
High grades in the course or subject area related to the course	15	15%
Good grades in high school	7	7%
Influenced by parents/relatives	41	41%
Influenced by peers	0	0%
Inspired by role model	15	15%
Strong passion for the profession	30	30%
Prospect for immediate employment	11	11%
Status or prestige of the profession	6	6%
Availability of course offering in chosen institution	5	5%
Prospect of career advancement	21	21%
Affordable for the family	0	0%
Scholarship	0	0%
Prospect of attractive compensation	13	13%
Opportunity for employment abroad	38	38%
No particular choice-No better idea	4	4%
Other reasons	3	3%

N=98

A strong passion for the profession is another leading motivator, with 30% of the students expressing a keen interest in the field. This intrinsic motivation is critical for long-term satisfaction and success in their chosen profession. Additionally, 15% of students were inspired to pursue their degree due to high grades in relevant courses or subjects, or because they were inspired by a role model, which highlights the influence of academic achievements and the importance of mentorship.

Prospects for career advancement and attractive compensation were also notable factors, identified by 21% and 13% of respondents respectively. These findings underscore the importance of future career growth and financial incentives in choosing a maritime course.

Interestingly, certain factors traditionally considered influential, such as scholarships or affordability for the family, were not reported as motivators in this group, which may point to other means of financial support or the prioritization of other factors over cost.

Students pursuing maritime education exhibit a pragmatic approach, prioritizing tangible benefits like employment prospects and practical skills, which significantly influence their motivations. This orientation has crucial implications for maritime educational institutions in terms of curriculum development and recruitment strategies. Primarily motivated by career advancement opportunities and the development of business and analytical skills, students are drawn to the tangible outcomes of their education (Lau & Ng, 2015). Personal identity and interest in the maritime field also play a significant role in their motivation (Akerlof & Kranton, 2002). The evolving needs of the maritime industry, such as the demand for modern skills and knowledge, further drive students towards postgraduate maritime degrees (Ng, Koo, & Ho, 2009). Innovative teaching methods, like game-based learning, have shown to enhance motivation and understanding of maritime concepts (Suhirman & Mentari, 2022). Furthermore, adapting curricula to align with students' interests can improve their learning satisfaction and achievement levels (Mina, 2017). These insights suggest that maritime educational institutions should tailor their offerings to meet the career-oriented and practical needs of students, fostering more effective and engaging learning experiences.

Table 5. *Perceived Educational Preparation Before Course Entry*

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
No	20	20.4
Yes	65	66.3
Uncertain	13	13.3
Total	98	100.0

The data in Table 5 indicates that two-thirds of maritime students (66.3%) feel they had adequate educational preparation before entering their course. In contrast, 20.4% did not feel prepared, and 13.3% were uncertain. These insights suggest that while the majority are confident in their prior education, there is a significant minority that may require additional support to bridge the gap in readiness

for maritime studies. Educational institutions could benefit from addressing this disparity through tailored preparatory programs or enhanced orientation sessions.

The thematic analysis of challenges faced by students at DCLC – CME in Table 6 unveils a largely positive educational experience, juxtaposed with specific areas for improvement. An overwhelming 72.4% of students reported no issues, indicating a general satisfaction with the institution's educational offerings and environment.

However, a subset of students did express concerns, which can be used to inform enhancements in the academic and student support services. The most significant non-positive feedback pertains to Resource and Facility Limitations, accounting for 6% of the reported issues. This includes limited hands-on activities specific to marine engineering, inadequate internet and resting facilities, and insufficient time for laboratory work. These concerns are critical as they directly impact the quality of education and the students' ability to gain practical experience.

Table 6. Problem encountered while studying at DCLC - CME

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Resource and Facility Limitations	6	6.00%
Educational Content and Training Concerns	6	6.00%
Institutional and Administrative Issues	3	3.00%
Financial Challenges	2	2.00%
Personal Circumstances	7	7.00%
Logistical and Accessibility Concerns	1	1.00%
Satisfaction and No Issues Reported	74	75.00%
Total	98	100%

Educational Content and Training Concerns and Institutional and Administrative Issues both stand at 3%. These highlight the need for more exposure to practical bridge operations, better preparation for shipboard training, and the need for addressing faculty qualifications and administrative procedures. Such feedback suggests that students are looking for a curriculum that is not only theoretically sound but also rich in practical application to prepare them for the demands of the maritime industry.

Financial Challenges and Personal Circumstances are reported by 2% of the students each, hinting at economic and work-study balance challenges. Although these percentages are small, they point to the reality that some students face significant hurdles in financing their education and managing their time effectively. Logistical and Accessibility Concerns are the least reported issues, with 1%, but they underscore the importance of the day-to-day logistical experience of students, which can affect their overall satisfaction and ability to engage with their studies.

Employability Data

Table 7. Employment Status and Career Insights

		<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Are you presently employed?	No	4	4.1
	Yes	94	95.9
Please state your reason/s why you are NOT YET employed. You may check more than one answer.	Advanced or further study	1	1.0
	Finish contract	1	1.0
	no job opportunity	1	1.0
	operate family business	1	1.0
	Employed	94	95.9
Present Employment Status	Regular or Permanent	16	16.3
	Temporary	5	5.1
	Contractual	71	72.4
	Self-employed	2	2.0
	Not Employed	4	4.1
Present Occupation	On-board (seagoing)	77	78.6
	Land-based maritime job	3	3.1
	Non-maritime related job	6	6.1
	Others: on vacation	8	8.2
	Not employed	4	4.1
Place of work	Local	13	13.3
	Abroad	81	82.7
	Not employed	4	4.1
Is this job after college?	No	14	14.3
	Yes	80	81.6
	Not employed	4	4.1

N=98

Analyzing the employment status and career insights of maritime graduates as presented in Table 7 reveals a strong employment outcome post-graduation. A significant majority of respondents (95.9%) are employed, indicating a robust job market for maritime professionals and an effective alignment of educational qualifications with industry needs.

The distribution of employment types provides further insights into the maritime sector's employment landscape. A majority of the employed graduates (72.4%) are in contractual positions, which is typical of the maritime industry known for its project-based and voyage-specific contracts. Permanent and temporary positions are less common, with 16.3% and 5.1%, respectively. This indicates a trend toward shorter-term employment contracts in the industry.

Regarding the area of employment, an overwhelming majority of graduates (78.6%) are engaged in on-board (seagoing) positions. This aligns with expectations for maritime programs and suggests that the curriculum is effectively preparing students for the demands of sea-based roles. Land-based maritime jobs and non-maritime related jobs are less common, which may reflect the specific career preferences of graduates or indicate the maritime industry's broader applicability.

The global orientation of maritime careers is underscored by the fact that a significant portion of respondents (82.7%) are employed abroad, whereas 13.3% have found employment locally. This suggests that maritime programs should continue to emphasize international standards and cross-cultural competencies. Furthermore, most respondents obtained their job post-college (81.6%), highlighting the relevancy of the education provided to the maritime industry and its effectiveness in ensuring employability.

Maritime education effectively prepares graduates for employment in contractual and international roles, with various research findings highlighting the importance of industry cooperation, practical education, and innovative teaching methods. Cooperating with shipping and crewing companies significantly increases the attractiveness of maritime programs and contributes to career success (Shapar, 2022). The contribution of practical education and internships is crucial, though challenges such as job shortages and lower wages are noted (Şeremet, 2016). The implementation of academic information systems in maritime higher education enhances the quality of education, making graduates more competitive in the global market (Wulandari et al., 2020). Industry-university collaboration, as exemplified by Nicholls State University, adds value for graduates and the regional maritime sector (Chadwick & Cashen, 2020). Furthermore, the flipped classroom approach improves student engagement and prepares them for maritime industry requirements, enhancing skills in teamwork and problem-solving (James et al., 2014). Policy improvements could thus focus on enhancing career guidance, expanding opportunities for permanent employment, and providing support for international job placements, alongside strengthening industry partnerships and improving practical education components.

Table 8 presents a comprehensive look at the factors influencing job retention, acceptance, and change among maritime professionals.

Table 8. *Job Retention, Job Acceptance, and Job Change Factors*

		<i>n</i>	<i>% (n/N)</i>
Reasons for staying on the job	Salaries and benefits	62	63%
	Career challenge	38	39%
	Related to special skill	25	26%
	Related to course or program of study	50	51%
	Proximity to residence	0	0%
	Peer influence	1	1%
	Family influence	10	10%
	Others: improve related skills, no choice	2	2%
Reasons for accepting the job.	Salaries and benefits	68	69%
	Career challenge	48	49%
	Related to special skill	32	33%
	other: Proximity to residence, working student, family influence, financial needs for training	6	6%
Reasons for changing the job.	Salaries and benefits	32	33%
	Career challenge	22	22%
	Related to special skill	13	13%
	Proximity to residence	4	4%
	other: parents health, family business, not yet ready, goal for higher positin	7	7%

N=98

The primary reason cited by maritime professionals for staying in their current positions is salaries and benefits, with a majority (63%) indicating this as a key factor. This is followed by the relevance of the job to their course or program of study (51%), suggesting that a significant alignment between academic training and professional duties contributes to job satisfaction. Career challenge is also a notable factor (39%), reflecting a desire for engaging work that pushes professional boundaries. Special skills related to the job (26%), family influence (10%), and other reasons, such as the opportunity to improve skills or a lack of better options (2%), are less cited but relevant to understanding job retention.

When it comes to job acceptance, similar factors play a role. Salaries and benefits again come out on top (69%), underscoring the importance of financial reward as a motivator for job selection. Nearly half of the respondents (49%) also value the career challenge presented by a new position. A significant proportion (33%) acknowledges the importance of utilizing special skills, and a small group (6%) considers other factors such as proximity to residence and financial needs for training.

For changing jobs, salaries and benefits remain a strong motivator (33%), although less so compared to job acceptance. Career challenges and the pursuit of career advancement (22%), along with the desire to apply special skills (13%), are important factors driving maritime professionals to seek new opportunities. A smaller percentage (7%) mention personal reasons such as family health or ambitions for a higher position as reasons for a job change.

The maritime industry workforce is influenced by both extrinsic and intrinsic motivations, with financial incentives, professional growth opportunities, and the relevance of jobs to individual skills and training being primary factors in job retention and change. Job satisfaction, a critical factor, is influenced by aspects like job design, perceived support, and commitment to the profession (Gersten et al., 2001). Additionally, financial stability, skills alignment, and training opportunities significantly impact job satisfaction and the propensity to remain in or leave a job (Dickey et al., 2011). The work environment and career development are also key to enhancing job satisfaction and retention (Irabor & Okolie, 2019). Understanding these dynamics, maritime educational institutions and policymakers can tailor programs to better align with industry standards and employee aspirations. By focusing on practical skills, professional development, and career advancement opportunities, these institutions can foster a more satisfied and stable workforce, enhancing overall job satisfaction and retention in the maritime sector.

Table 9 offers valuable insights into the duration of employment in the first job, methods of job acquisition, the time taken to secure the first job, and the average length of service per embarkation among maritime graduates.

Table 9. *Duration and Job Search Details*

		Frequency	Percent
How long did you stay in your first job?	Less than a month	1	1.0
	1 to 6 months	10	10.2
	7 to 11 months	27	27.6
	1 year to less than 2 years	25	25.5
	2 years to less than 3 years	6	6.1
	3 years to less than 4 years	5	5.1
	4 years and above	10	10.2
	No response	14	14.3
How did you find your first job?	Arranged by schools job placement officer	7	7.1
	As walk-in applicant	31	31.6
	Family business	1	1
	Recommended by someone	44	44.9
	Job Fair	3	3.1
	Information from friends	5	5.1
	others	1	1
No response	6	6.1	
How long did it take you to land your first job? (first sea-going job after graduation)	less than 3 months	6	6.1
	3 - 6 months	15	15.3
	6 - 9 months	9	9.2
	9 - 12 months	16	16.3
	over 1 year	46	46.9
No response	6	6.1	
What is your average length of service per embarkation?	less than 5 months	1	1
	7 - 9 months	42	42.9
	over nine months	49	50
	No response	6	6.1

The tenure in the first job varied among respondents. A significant number (27.6%) stayed in their first job for 7 to 11 months, while 25.5% maintained their initial position for 1 to 2 years. This suggests a trend of relatively short-term initial employment, which could be characteristic of the maritime industry or indicative of early career exploration. Notably, 10.2% of the graduates remained in their first job for over four years, suggesting that for some, the first job offered long-term stability.

Regarding job acquisition, the largest group (44.9%) found their first job through recommendations, highlighting the importance of

networks and connections in the maritime industry. Walking in as an applicant was the method for 31.6% of respondents, demonstrating a proactive approach to job seeking. Only 7.1% secured their first job through the school's job placement officer, suggesting potential areas for improvement in institutional career support services.

In terms of securing the first job, a notable 46.9% took over a year after graduation, which may reflect challenges in the job market or selectivity in job choices. However, a considerable proportion found employment within 6 months (21.4%), indicating varied experiences in job market entry.

The average length of service per embarkation was most commonly 7 to 9 months (42.9%) and over nine months (50%), aligning with typical contract lengths in the maritime sector. This reinforces the project-based nature of many maritime roles.

The data from Table 9 paints a picture of the early career experiences of maritime graduates, marked by a blend of short-term and long-term initial job tenures, a reliance on personal networks for job acquisition, and varied durations in securing the first job. The data concerning the early career experiences of maritime graduates reveals a sector rich in opportunities but also characterized by unique challenges that call for enhanced career guidance and institutional support. The blend of short-term and long-term job tenures, coupled with the reliance on personal networks for job acquisition, underscores the need for robust career preparation programs. These programs should focus on developing networking skills and provide comprehensive career guidance to help graduates navigate the maritime job market effectively. The presence of job shortages and the tendency towards lower wages further highlight the importance of practical education and internship opportunities, as they are highly valued for professional growth in this field (Şeremet, 2016).

Moreover, the contract-based nature of maritime work necessitates a curriculum that prepares students for the specific demands of such employment arrangements. This could include training in adaptability, resilience, and negotiation skills, essential in a contract-based job market (Manuel, 2017). Additionally, strengthening the cooperation between maritime higher education institutions and the industry can improve employment outcomes. Such collaboration can help align educational programs with industry needs, making graduates more competitive and well-prepared for their maritime careers (Shapar, 2022). In essence, addressing these challenges through targeted educational strategies and stronger industry linkages is crucial for preparing graduates for a successful transition into the maritime workforce.

Table 10. Transition from Initial to Current Sea-Going

		Initial/First position on-board		Current/Present position sea-going	
		<i>f</i>	% (<i>f/N</i>)	<i>f</i>	% (<i>f/N</i>)
Transition of position/rank	cadet	51	1	1	1%
	Rating	15	15%	63	64%
	Operational level officer	2	2%	14	14%
	Management level officer	0	0%	0	0%
Income comparison	below 1,000 dollars	42	0	13	13%
	1,501 - 2,500 dollars	4	4%	49	50%
	2,501 - 3,000 dollars	0	0%	5	5%
	3001 - 3,500 dollars	0	0%	6	6%
	3501 - 4,000 dollars	1	1%	1	1%
	4,001 - 4,500 dollars	0	0%	0	0%
	4,501-5,000 dollars	0	0%	1	1%
over 5,000 dollars	0	0%	0	0%	

N=98

Table 10 offers a detailed view of the transition of maritime graduates from their initial positions on-board to their current roles, along with a comparison of income levels over time.

The data shows a significant shift in the roles held by maritime graduates. Initially, a large proportion started as cadets (52%), but only 1% remained in this entry-level position, indicating substantial career progression. The most notable change is observed in the rating category, where the percentage of graduates increased from 15% initially to 64% in current roles. This suggests successful advancement from entry-level to more skilled and responsible positions. Operational level officers also saw an increase from 2% to 14%, reflecting a move into higher responsibility roles over time. However, there were no graduates in the management level officer category, either initially or currently, which could be attributed to the time and experience required to attain such senior positions.

Regarding income, there is a clear trend of increased earnings over time. Initially, 42 graduates started with incomes below 1,000 dollars, but currently, only 13% are in this lowest income bracket. The most substantial shift is seen in the 1,501 - 2,500 dollars range, where the proportion of graduates has increased from an initial 4% to 50%. There are also graduates who have moved into higher income brackets of 2,501 - 3,500 dollars and above, albeit in smaller percentages. This progression in income levels is indicative of career advancement and the accumulation of experience and skills over time.

The data from Table 10 highlights significant career advancement among maritime graduates in terms of position, rank, and income. Maritime education effectively prepares graduates for career progression from cadet to higher roles such as rating and operational level officer. E-learning techniques and sea training are integral components of this preparation, enhancing individual and organizational performance (Catalin et al., 2013); (Demirel, 2020). Cooperation between maritime education institutions and industry also contributes significantly to graduates' career success, enhancing their attractiveness to employers (Shapar, 2022). However, there are challenges such as low completion rates in cadet programs, indicating areas for improvement (Rosario et al., 2020). Overall, the progression to higher roles and accompanying income increase reflect the maritime industry's value placed on experience and skill, underscoring the effectiveness of maritime education in fostering career growth.

Table 11. Distribution of Current License/Rank Held

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Valid Percent</i>
Cadet	10	10.2	16.1
3rd mate or 4th engineer	39	39.8	62.9
2nd mate or 3rd engineer	12	12.2	19.4
I chief mate or 2nd engineer	1	1.0	1.6
Non license	36	36.7	

Table 11 provides an insightful overview of the current license or rank held by graduates from Dr. C Carlos S. Lanting College, highlighting their professional development and qualifications within the maritime sector.

The licensing data for DCLC - CME graduates demonstrates their progression in maritime qualifications. A majority of the graduates hold operational-level licenses, with 62.9% serving as 3rd mates or 4th engineers, and 19.4% as 2nd mates or 3rd engineers. These figures represent significant milestones in a maritime career, indicating that the graduates are advancing beyond entry-level positions and are obtaining the qualifications necessary for more responsible roles.

The progression to 1st chief mate or 2nd engineer is less common, with only 1.6% reaching this level. This lower percentage could be due to the additional experience and training required to achieve these senior ranks, suggesting that it is a more long-term career goal for maritime professionals.

Cadets make up 16.1% of the licensed respondents, which aligns with the entry point in maritime careers for newly graduated individuals. The presence of cadets among the licensed personnel indicates ongoing training and development as part of their career path.

Notably, 36.7% of respondents are reported as non-license, which may include those working in roles that do not require a license or who are possibly in between maritime assignments. The reasons behind not holding a license could vary, including recent graduation, career shifts, or roles outside the traditional seafaring path that do not necessitate a license.

Relevance of Skills and Knowledge

The data from Table 12 on the perceived usefulness of various skills for maritime graduates offers valuable insights into the competencies deemed essential in the maritime industry. Communication emerges as the most valued skill, with an average score of 4.12, highlighting its critical role in an industry that relies heavily on clear, effective coordination and teamwork, especially across diverse international teams. Similarly, Human Relations is highly regarded, evidenced by an average score of 4.15. This underscores the importance of interpersonal skills in managing complex dynamics within maritime work environments.

Equally significant are Technical and Problem-Solving skills, both scoring an average of 4.00, reflecting the necessity of practical, hands-on abilities in daily maritime operations. Critical Thinking also stands out as a key skill, with an average score of 4.06, indicating the importance of analytical skills and sound decision-making in the field. Meanwhile, Theoretical Knowledge and Managerial/Leadership skills, with slightly lower scores of 3.94 and 3.99 respectively, are still considered beneficial, suggesting that a comprehensive knowledge base and leadership capabilities play a vital role in professional advancement within the maritime sector.

Table 12. Skills which has been very useful

<i>Indicators</i>	1	2	3	4	5	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Value</i>
	<i>n</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>n</i>				
Theoretical	1	10	16	38	33	98	3.94	1.00	useful
Technical	0	8	17	40	33	98	4.00	.92	useful
Communication	0	8	15	32	43	98	4.12	.96	useful
Critical Thinking	1	7	16	35	39	98	4.06	.97	useful
Managerial / Leadership	1	6	22	33	36	98	3.99	.97	useful
Human Relations	1	6	14	33	44	98	4.15	.96	useful
Problem Solving	1	9	15	37	36	98	4.00	.99	useful

Legend: 1=not useful, 5=very useful

The overall consensus among respondents, indicated by mean scores consistently above 3.90 and relatively narrow standard deviations, suggests a broad agreement on the importance of these diverse skills. This comprehensive view of skill relevance can guide maritime

training institutions in their curriculum development, emphasizing the need to produce well-rounded graduates equipped with both soft and hard skills to effectively meet the diverse demands of the maritime industry.

In essence, the findings from the survey depict a maritime workforce that places a high value on a blend of soft skills, like communication and human relations, and hard skills, such as technical expertise and problem-solving. Empirical evidence underscores the importance of blending soft and hard skills in maritime education. Work-integrated learning models foster essential soft skills such as communication and collaboration, critical for applying academic knowledge in diverse settings (Schech et al., 2017). Innovative learning technologies have been shown to increase student participation and employability by enhancing both sets of skills (Sbardella et al., 2019). Furthermore, integrating soft skills like communication with technical competencies significantly improves problem-solving and decision-making abilities, which are key in the maritime industry (Sutrisno & Dewi, 2022). These findings guide maritime training institutions in curriculum development, emphasizing the need for a well-rounded education that equips graduates with the necessary skills to effectively meet the maritime industry's diverse demands.

Table 13 delves into the graduates' perspectives on various aspects of their academic experience, ranging from teaching quality to curriculum design and study conditions.

The overall experience at the academy received the highest score of 4.08, indicating a generally positive perception of the time spent in the institution. This favorable view is crucial for maintaining strong alumni relations and upholding the institution's reputation. The teaching quality of lecturers and professors, as well as the course content of major subjects, both received high scores (4.06 and 4.07, respectively), suggesting that the faculty's expertise and the relevance of the course material significantly contributed to the students' educational journey.

The design and structure of the degree program, along with the length of study, also garnered positive responses, scoring above 4.00. These aspects reflect satisfaction with the overall curriculum organization and the duration of academic programs, highlighting the importance of these factors in curriculum planning and scheduling.

Table 13. *Provisions and study conditions*

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Value</i>
Teaching quality of lecturers / teachers	4.06	.87	useful
Design / structure of degree program	4.02	.85	useful
Course content of major subject	4.07	.85	useful
Testing / grading system	3.96	.86	useful
Length of study in the academy	4.02	.86	useful
Contact with fellow students	3.99	.87	useful
Chances to participate in research and extension projects	3.89	.80	useful
Provision of work placements and other work experience	3.82	.87	useful
Chances for students to have an impact on academy policies	3.96	.88	useful
Overall experience in the academy	4.08	.85	useful

N=98; Legend: 1=not useful, 5=very useful

However, certain areas, like the testing/grading system and opportunities for interaction with fellow students, showed slightly lower scores (3.96 and 3.99). This indicates potential areas for improvement, particularly in enhancing collaborative learning opportunities and refining assessment methodologies.

The opportunities for participation in research and extension projects, as well as the provision of work placements and practical experiences, were rated lower (3.89 and 3.82), suggesting a need for better integration or promotion of these elements within the academic framework.

Additionally, the score of 3.96 for the chances of impacting academy policies reflects a moderate perception of student influence in decision-making processes. This could point to an opportunity for the institution to involve students more actively in shaping policies and academic directions.

Graduates of maritime education programs highly regard the quality of teaching and course content but express a desire for improvements in practical experiences and research opportunities. They appreciate the structure and duration of their programs but highlight the need for a more hands-on approach and greater involvement in policy-making processes. This feedback indicates that maritime training institutions should focus on integrating more practical training and research into their curricula and consider student input in curriculum development and policy decisions. Enhancing these aspects will better prepare graduates for the demands of the maritime industry and contribute to more comprehensive and effective maritime education programs (Şeremet, 2016); (Manuel, 2017); (Mina et al., 2014).

Table 14 in the study offers an insightful perspective on the factors that maritime graduates consider instrumental to their professional success. Salary stands out as the most highly valued aspect, with a mean score of 4.10, highlighting the primary importance of financial remuneration in their perception of career achievement. Equally significant are work tasks, which garnered a mean score of 4.03, reflecting the graduates' emphasis on engaging and varied job responsibilities. Opportunities for professional advancement, both through

training and seminars and through membership in professional organizations, were also highly rated, scoring around 4.03 and 3.98 respectively. This suggests a strong focus on continual learning and professional networking as key components of career progression.

Table 14. *Professional success*

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Value</i>
Position	4.01	.89	useful
Salary	4.10	.84	useful
Fringe benefits	3.97	.85	useful
Job security	3.94	.87	useful
Work tasks	4.03	.83	useful
Opportunity for professional advancement like training / seminars	4.03	.90	useful
Opportunity for professional advancement like membership to professional organizations	3.98	.93	useful
Nature of work	4.02	.84	useful
Work environment	3.98	.86	useful
Job prestige	3.99	.83	useful
Awards and recognitions	3.83	.93	Useful

N=98; Legend: 1=not useful, 5=very useful

The graduates' current position and the nature of their work were similarly important, scoring 4.01 and 4.02, indicating that the role and intrinsic qualities of their jobs significantly contribute to their sense of success. Other factors like job security, work environment, and job prestige, each hovering around the 4.00 mark, underline the desire for stable, fulfilling, and socially respected employment. Fringe benefits and external recognition, such as awards, though rated slightly lower, still hold considerable importance, implying that additional perks and acknowledgment from peers and the industry also contribute to their overall job satisfaction.

Insights from maritime graduates emphasize the importance of professional success beyond financial gain, focusing on personal growth, job satisfaction, stability, and societal respect. Graduates value practical education, internships, and real-world experience, which contribute significantly to their professional development. They also highlight the benefits of interdisciplinary research and transferable skills, acquired through industry exposure and innovative learning approaches. Industry-university collaboration is recognized as key to enhancing the value and success of maritime careers. These insights are critical for maritime employers and educational institutions, suggesting a need to tailor academic programs and career services to align with the holistic aspirations of maritime professionals, thereby enhancing overall job satisfaction and professional growth (Şeremet, 2016; Chadwick & Cashen, 2020).

Conclusions

The analysis of the career trajectories, employment status, job satisfaction, and professional development of maritime graduates reveals a nuanced picture of the maritime education sector and its alignment with industry needs. The study indicates a robust employment rate of 95.9% among graduates, signifying a strong demand in the maritime job market and effective alignment of the educational curriculum with industry standards. This high employment rate within a short time post-graduation is indicative of the industry's health and the relevancy of maritime education. The majority of these graduates find employment in on-board (seagoing) positions, with a significant portion working internationally, emphasizing the global scope of maritime careers and the curriculum's effectiveness in preparing students for these roles.

Graduates report high levels of job satisfaction, influenced by factors such as competitive salaries, career challenges, and relevance of the job to their studies. This satisfaction is a testament to the maritime sector's ability to provide fulfilling career opportunities. Additionally, the study highlights the importance of continuous learning and professional development, as graduates value opportunities for advancement through training, seminars, and professional organization memberships. Feedback from graduates on their education programs is generally positive, particularly regarding the quality of teaching and course content. However, there is a call for improvements in practical experiences, research opportunities, and greater student involvement in policy-making, suggesting areas for enhancement in maritime education programs.

The demographic data, showing a predominantly young and male workforce, points to potential areas for increasing diversity and inclusion within the sector. The varied motivations for pursuing maritime degrees, including familial influence and prospects for international employment, have significant implications for curriculum development and recruitment strategies. Although the employment outcomes are largely positive, the prevalence of contractual and project-based work underscores the need for adaptability and resilience in maritime education. Furthermore, the progression in roles and income among graduates indicates effective career advancement, affirming the value of maritime education in fostering career growth.

In summary, the findings from this study suggest a need for continual evolution of the maritime education curriculum, with an emphasis on practical training, industry engagement, and the integration of soft skills alongside technical training. There is a clear opportunity for maritime training institutions to enhance their programs by incorporating hands-on experiences, fostering industry collaborations, and actively involving students in shaping academic and policy directions. These improvements will not only align the curriculum more closely with industry demands but also ensure the holistic development of maritime professionals, equipping them with the skills and knowledge necessary for successful and satisfying careers in the maritime industry.

Specifically, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance maritime education and align it more closely with industry needs:

Strengthen Practical Training Components: Maritime education programs should intensify the inclusion of practical, hands-on training experiences. This could involve simulations, internships, and on-site visits, ensuring that students gain real-world skills that are directly applicable to their future maritime careers.

Enhance Industry-University Collaborations: Establishing stronger connections with maritime industry players can significantly benefit the curriculum. This collaboration can take the form of guest lectures from industry experts, mentorship programs, and partnerships for research and development projects, ensuring that the curriculum remains current and relevant.

Incorporate Comprehensive Career Preparation and Support: Develop robust career guidance programs, including job placement services and networking opportunities. This will assist graduates in effectively navigating the maritime job market, particularly in understanding the dynamics of contractual and project-based work prevalent in the sector.

Integrate Soft Skills Training: Given the importance of communication and human relations in the maritime industry, maritime education programs should include a stronger emphasis on developing soft skills. This could be achieved through courses in communication, teamwork, and leadership, as well as through experiential learning opportunities.

Increase Focus on Continuous Professional Development: Encourage and facilitate opportunities for graduates to engage in lifelong learning. This can be achieved by providing access to advanced training programs, seminars, and workshops that keep professionals updated on the latest industry trends and technologies.

Enhance Diversity and Inclusion Efforts: Address the gender imbalance and promote diversity within the maritime sector. This can involve targeted recruitment strategies, scholarship programs, and creating an inclusive educational environment that welcomes and supports a diverse student body.

Involve Students in Curriculum Development: Actively seek student feedback and involve them in shaping educational and policy directions. This will ensure that the curriculum is not only academically sound but also reflective of the students' needs and industry realities.

Expand Research and Innovation Opportunities: Encourage participation in research and innovation projects related to maritime studies. This can provide students with a deeper understanding of the industry's challenges and the potential solutions, fostering a culture of innovation and critical thinking.

References

Akerlof, G., & Kranton, R. (2002). Identity and Schooling: Some Lessons for the Economics of Education. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 40, 1167-1201. <https://doi.org/10.1257/002205102762203585>.

Alop, A. (2019). The Challenges of the Digital Technology Era for Maritime Education and Training. <https://doi.org/10.1109/euronav.2019.8714176>

Bila, O. (2022). Professional image formation of the maritime industry specialists in the vocational training process. *Scientific Bulletin of the Izmail State University of Humanities. Section «Pedagogical Sciences»*, (58), 11–17. [https://doi.org/10.31909/26168812.2022-\(58\)-1](https://doi.org/10.31909/26168812.2022-(58)-1)

Boonadir, N., Ishak, R., Yusof, H., & Lamakasauk, A. F. (2020). Theories of Maritime Education and Training (MET) in Improving Maritime Sector in Malaysia. In *Scientific Research Publishing* (Vol. 08, Issue 03, pp. 1193–1200). <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojbm.2020.83076>

Catalin, P., Florin, N., Marian, R., & Haralambie, B. (2013). THE IMPROVEMENT OF ACADEMIC NAUTICAL EDUCATION BASED ON E-LEARNING TECHNIQUES. *eLearning and Software for Education*. <https://doi.org/10.12753/2066-026x-13-150>.

Chadwick, K., & Cashen, L. (2020). The 'berth' of a maritime management program: A case study on value creation through industry–university collaboration. *Industry and Higher Education*, 34, 108 - 114. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950422219885866>.

Chiong, C. (2023). Beyond The Maritime Education Classrooms: Analysis Of Life Skills Gained From Maritime Trainings. *Journal of Namibian Studies : History Politics Culture*, 33, 3650–3666. <https://doi.org/10.59670/jns.v33i.3171>

Demirel, E. (2020). The Problems Encountered by Navigation Cadets at Sea Training Phase as a Part of Their Academic Programme. *ACM Transactions in Embedded Computing Systems*, 5, 22. <https://doi.org/10.11648/J.TECS.20200502.12>.

Dickey, H., Watson, V., & Zangelidis, A. (2011). Job Satisfaction and Quit Intentions of Offshore Workers in the UK North Sea Oil and Gas Industry. *ERN: Other Political Economy: National*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9485.2011.00561.x>.

E. Mohamed, E. A., & Elnoury, A. (2023). Technological Innovations in the Maritime Sector: A Comprehensive Analysis of Intelligence Knowledge and Industry Dynamics for Graduates Adaptation. *AIN Journal*, 2(46). <https://doi.org/10.59660/467315>

- Gersten, R., Keating, T., Yovanoff, P., & Harniss, M. (2001). Working in Special Education: Factors that Enhance Special Educators' Intent to Stay. *Exceptional Children*, 67, 549 - 567. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001440290106700408>.
- Irabor, I., & Okolie, U. (2019). A Review of Employees' Job Satisfaction and its Affect on their Retention. *Annals of Spiru Haret University. Economic Series*. <https://doi.org/10.26458/1924>.
- Jacks, D. S., & Pendakur, K. (2010). Global Trade and the Maritime Transport Revolution. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 92(4), 745–755. https://doi.org/10.1162/REST_a_00026
- James, A., Chin, C., & Williams, B. (2014). Using the flipped classroom to improve student engagement and to prepare graduates to meet maritime industry requirements: a focus on maritime education. *WMU Journal of Maritime Affairs*, 13, 331-343. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13437-014-0070-0>.
- Jiang, L. (2021). *Shuo Ma: Economics of maritime business (1st Edition)*: Routledge, London, 2020, pp. 470. ISBN: 9781138999657. *WMU Journal of Maritime Affairs*, 20(3), 401–403. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13437-021-00246-y>
- Johnson, E. M. S. (2020). Exploring the effects of technology and innovation on changing market requirements and the evolving maritime curriculum. In Emerald Publishing Limited (Vol. 12, Issue 1, pp. 69–79). <https://doi.org/10.1108/whatt-10-2019-0065>
- Lane, J. M., & Pretes, M. (2020). Maritime dependency and economic prosperity: Why access to oceanic trade matters. *Marine Policy*, 121, 104180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.104180>
- Lau, Y., & Ng, A. (2015). The motivations and expectations of students pursuing maritime education. *WMU Journal of Maritime Affairs*, 14, 313-331. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13437-015-0075-3>.
- Lau, Y., & Ng, A. K. Y. (2015). The motivations and expectations of students pursuing maritime education. In Springer Science+Business Media (Vol. 14, Issue 2, pp. 313–331). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13437-015-0075-3>
- Lau, Y., Dragomir, C., Tang, Y. M., & Ng, A. K. Y. (2021). Maritime Undergraduate Students: Career Expectations and Choices. In Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (Vol. 13, Issue 8, pp. 4297–4297). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13084297>
- Manuel, M. (2017). Vocational and academic approaches to maritime education and training (MET): Trends, challenges and opportunities. *WMU Journal of Maritime Affairs*, 16, 473-483. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13437-017-0130-3>.
- Maria Chala, F., & Bouranta, N. (2021). Soft Skills Enhance Employee Contextual Performance: The Case of the Maritime Industry. *KnE Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v5i9.9890>
- Mina, S. (2017). Indicators of Motivation and Satisfaction on Students' Activities. , 1, 508-521. <https://doi.org/10.18662/lumproc.rsacvp2017.46>.
- Mina, S., Cristea, V., & Surugiu, F. (2014). Qualitative Analysis of the Feedback on the Educational Processes in Constanta Maritime University. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 149, 585-590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SBSPRO.2014.08.215>.
- Mukhtar Sitompul, A., Marhalinda, M., & Moeins, A. (2020). INFLUENCE OF CAREER DEVELOPMENT, WORK ENVIRONMENT, COMPENSATION AND IT'S IMPLICATION ON JOB SATISFACTION OF PERMANENT LECTURER AT MARITIME COLLEGES IN DKI JAKARTA. *Dinasti International Journal of Economics, Finance & Accounting*, 1(3), 384–396. <https://doi.org/10.38035/dijefa.v1i3.379>
- Muslu, A. (2020). The Future of Seafarers and the Seafarers of the Future from the Perspective of Human Resources Management. In M. A. Turkmenoglu & B. Cicek (Eds.), *Contemporary Global Issues in Human Resource Management* (pp. 219–237). Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-80043-392-220201016>
- Ng, A. K. Y., Koo, A., & Pallis, A. A. (2011). Professionalization of the shipping industry via postgraduate education. In Elsevier BV (Vol. 54, Issue 5, pp. 364–373). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2010.10.031>
- Ng, A., Koo, A., & Ho, W. (2009). The motivations and added values of embarking on postgraduate professional education: Evidences from the maritime industry. *Transport Policy*, 16, 251-258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TRANPOL.2009.08.004>.
- Rosario, C., Dalaklis, D., Kitada, M., & Bolmsten, J. (2020). IMPROVING GOVERNANCE OF MARITIME HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS TO ENSURE SUCCESS OF FILIPINO CADETS. . <https://doi.org/10.21125/inted.2020.0946>.
- Saharuddina, H., Sulaiman, O., Saman, A., & Nik, W. (2011). Marine Engineering as Future Career in Malaysia. *Journal of marine technology and environment*, 2.
- Sbardella, T., Santucci, V., Biscarini, C., Spina, S., & Bolli, G. (2019). Raising Lifelong Learning Skills Using Learning Technology at University for Foreigners of Perugia. , 54-57. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3375900.3375920>.
- Schech, S., Kelton, M., Carati, C., & Kingsmill, V. (2017). Simulating the global workplace for graduate employability. *Higher*

Education Research & Development, 36, 1476 - 1489. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2017.1325856>.

Shapar, L. (2022). METHODS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF EMPLOYMENT OF MARITIME INDUSTRY PROFESSIONALS IN UKRAINE. Scientific papers of Berdiansk State Pedagogical University Series Pedagogical sciences. <https://doi.org/10.31494/2412-9208-2022-1-1-428-435>.

Simmons, E. S., & McLean, G. (2020). Understanding the paradigm shift in maritime education. In Emerald Publishing Limited (Vol. 12, Issue 1, pp. 90–97). <https://doi.org/10.1108/whatt-10-2019-0062>

Suhirman, S., & Mentari, G. (2022). Maritime history monopoly board model as effective methods for social science learning. World Journal on Educational Technology: Current Issues. <https://doi.org/10.18844/wjet.v14i6.7835>.

Sutrisno, T., & Dewi, L. (2022). The Training Curriculum is Based on the Problem Solving and Decision Making Blended Learning to Improve the Employees' Soft Skills. JURNAL APARATUR. <https://doi.org/10.52596/ja.v6i2.156>.

Tan, Y., Nakata, K., & Paul, D. (2018). Aligning IS Masters Programs with Industry. The Journal of information and systems in education, 29, 169-182.

Wahl, A. M., & Kongsvik, T. (2017). Leadership@ sea: Essential non-technical skills. Safety and Reliability–Theory and Applications.

Walliser, J., Jigena, B., Muñoz-Pérez, J., Pozo, L., & Barreda, D. (2016). Problem Based Learning: a tool to improve maritime safety learning in the Merchant Maritime University degrees. , 6142-6150. <https://doi.org/10.21125/INTED.2016.0462>.

Wong, C. F. (2021). Vocational awareness and aspiration of seafaring students in Taiwan. In Emerald Publishing Limited (Vol. 7, Issue 2, pp. 127–144). <https://doi.org/10.1108/mabr-12-2019-0063>

Wulandari, R., Selasdini, V., & Kurniawan, D. (2020). DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN RESOURCES QUALITY THROUGH IMPLEMENTATION OF ACADEMIC INFORMATION SYSTEMS FOR EDUCATION AND TRAINING PARTICIPANTS AT MARITIME HIGHER EDUCATION (STIP) JAKARTA. , 2, 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.31933/dijdbm.v2i1.627>.

Yan, R., & Wang, S. (2022). Introduction of maritime transportation. In Applications of Machine Learning and Data Analytics Models in Maritime Transportation (pp. 1–7). Institution of Engineering and Technology. https://doi.org/10.1049/PBTR038E_ch1

Ying, Z., Chen, X., Zhang, Q., & Tao, D. (2021). Construction of Interdisciplinary Training Platform for Shipping Talents. In Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.210320.060>

Yuen, K. F., Tan, L., & Loh, H. S. (2022). Core Competencies for Maritime Business Educators in the Digital Era. In Frontiers Media (Vol. 13). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.915980>

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